

DESIGN OF SEMI-COMPLEX PARTS USING ANISOTROPIC CARBON FIBER CARD WEB REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

Y. Furuta^{1*}, S. SHAO¹, G. Yin¹, B. Xiao¹, Y. Wan¹, and J. Takahashi¹
¹Department of Systems Innovation, The University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan
 * Corresponding author (furuta-yasuyuki@cfrtp.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp)

Identifier:ICCM22-I/616

Introduction & Materials

about CFRP

The growth of world total fossil energy consumption is partly led by the increase of the energy consumed in the transport sector.

http://www.boeing.com/commercial/aeromagazine/articles/qtr_4_06/article_04_2.html

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have developed the weight saving of parts such as aerospace and pressure vessel so far.

- Lightness
- High mechanical property

<https://www.iea.org/statistics/kwes/consumption/>

about CWT (Carbon fiber card Web reinforced Thermoplastics)

- recycled carbon fiber
- anisotropic material

S30_CWT30%
 Stretch ratio = 30%
 Fiber volume fraction = 30%

Netting Theory

FOD (Fiber Orientation Distribution)

X-ray analysis

Netting Theory

$$\int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} f(\theta) d\theta = 1 \quad (-\pi/2 \leq \theta \leq \pi/2)$$

$$E_{11} = E_f V_f \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \cos^4 \theta f(\theta) d\theta$$

$$E_{22} = E_f V_f \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \sin^4 \theta f(\theta) d\theta$$

$$E_{12} = E_f V_f \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \cos^2 \theta \cdot \sin^2 \theta f(\theta) d\theta$$

$$E_L = E_{11} - \frac{E_{12}^2}{E_{22}}$$

$$E_T = E_{22} - \frac{E_{12}^2}{E_{11}}$$

$$G_{LT} = E_{12}$$

Mechanical Property

This graph shows us that Netting Theory can apply to the prediction of CWT mechanical property.

Fitting function

$$f(\theta) = a \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{0,180}^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\theta^2}{2\sigma_{0,180}^2}\right) + b \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{90}^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\theta-90)^2}{2\sigma_{90}^2}\right) + c \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{0,180}^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\theta-180)^2}{2\sigma_{0,180}^2}\right) + c$$

normal distribution normal distribution normal distribution constant

	$\sigma_{0,180}$	a	σ_{90}	b	c
S0_30%	83.198	89.815	0.129	14.480	0.607
S30_30%	70.900	110.285	0.118	11.725	0.406

	$\sigma_{0,180}$	a	σ_{90}	b	c
S0_40%	152.608	63.541	0.122	12.380	0.483
S48_40%	218.030	73.310	0.134	13.501	0.318

FEM model & Conclusion

Hat-shaped structure

The hat-shaped structure was used as a model of the semi-complex structure, and the optimization of mechanical properties was verified.

Conclusion

- ✓ It has been found that the mechanical properties of CWT can be calculated from FOD data by applying Netting Theory.
- ✓ It turned out that FOD data can be approximated by superposition of normal distribution.
- ✓ It is possible to optimize, by using the created FEM model, FOD and material mechanical property to be obtained by changing five parameters.

Acknowledgements

Part of this study was conducted as Japanese METI project "the Future Pioneering Projects/Innovative Structural Materials Project" since 2013 financial year. Authors would like to express sincerely appreciation to the project members who have provided valuable information and useful discussions

